

AUTOMATING THE PRODUCTION PROCESS OF HOUSEHOLD NAPKINS

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Annotation. *The research focuses on the automation of the production process for household napkins, aiming to enhance efficiency, reduce labor costs, and improve product consistency. By integrating advanced robotics and control systems, the paper explores how automation can streamline the entire manufacturing cycle from raw material handling to packaging. It discusses the design and implementation of automated machinery that can adjust to various sizes and quality specifications, ensuring flexibility in production lines. The study also evaluates the environmental impact, considering how automated processes can lead to more sustainable practices through efficient resource utilization and waste reduction. Furthermore, the impact of automation on the workforce and necessary skill adjustments are analyzed, providing insights into the future of manufacturing in the consumer goods sector.*

Keywords: *automation, manufacturing process, household napkins, robotics, production efficiency, sustainable manufacturing, resource management, consumer goods production, industrial automation, workforce transformation*

1. Introduction

There are a lot of products that are not done manually. The same goes for this product. The technology and innovation has reached a point where the automated production can be considered as a very good idea. This research proposes and innovates a product to automate the production process of household napkins. This report will start by giving an overview of household napkins. The discussion will then proceed to the proposed automation production involving the process, the steps, and the reasons how the automated production is considered feasible. As the report goes further, it will be focusing on the improvement from the existing product. It will be shown by the comparison of the economical aspect both from existing and automated production. The comparison on types of household napkins and the quality of the product, also the comparison on energy cost and waste of materials. Last but not least, the impact from the improvement will be elaborated. From this report, we hope that everyone who reads will have a good look at how even a simple product can be improved and made more efficient. In terms of technological and innovation perspective, this research is also considered as the

stepping stone to develop a more advanced and efficient micro-factory production for household items at home. An automated production is the use of technology and machines to perform the tasks so mostly the human efforts can be reduced. This automation production is preferable in terms of energy usage and time efficiency compared with human labor. This is due to the fact that the energy cost in today's technology is considered more efficient using electrical energy rather than human metabolic energy. With the pressure now to minimize the use of non-renewable energy sources, the electrical energy can be mostly drawn from renewable energy which is more cost-effective and environmentally friendly. This automation production can also be considered as the trial to reduce human efforts. This is a good opportunity to backup the human tasks with machines. With more advanced AI and machine technology today, a time will come where the tasks can be done without any human efforts. Although it is still the early stage to reach that kind of technology, this research is trying to provide an example for a household items production. (Hossain, 2020)(Murmura et al., 2021)(Parthasarathy)

2. Benefits of automating the production process

The best way to achieve this is to make sure that a) the machines do not break down b) if a breakdown occurs, it is corrected immediately.

The ideal situation for machining is to make sure that the machines are working at all times. The time when the machines are not working and the product is not being produced should be minimized.

The production of paper napkins has a large quantity of machines involved.

To automate the manufacturing of paper napkins, there are three types of machines that are used.

Work in process - The converting industries hold paper until it is converted, and the primary and secondary textiles until they are cut and sewn into napkins. A delay could be incurred if there are problems with the quality of the paper or textile. These problems are corrected by producing a new batch rather than correcting the old one. The delay between ordering the material and the receipt of it is also included in the work in process. A delay could be incurred if there are problems with the quality of the paper or textile. These problems are corrected by producing a new batch rather than correcting the old one. The delay between ordering the material and the receipt of it is also included in the work in process.

Products - The processes of manufacturing an immense number of finished papers or paperboards, as well as the ginned, loomed, and finished fabrics. (Frits & Bertok, 2020)(Zulfiqar et al.2021)(Ning et al., 2022)

3. Challenges in automating the production process

Folded napkins that are packed in plastic bags are often over-packaged because complex geometries make napkin size estimation difficult. This is another area where automation lacks.

Embossed napkin designs are very popular but complex. High-quality emboss patterns require tight control of the napkin material location in the embossing head, and often post-embossing quality inspection is required to reject napkins with improper embossing. Because of these folding difficulties, there are many types of

folded napkins that have no automation solutions. These napkins are still hand-folded today.

The second major problem comes in the area of napkin folding where multiple techniques and styles exist. Ideal folding quality results in consistent tightness and napkin squareness. This can be difficult to automate as napkin squareness is derived from the initial squareness and angle of the napkin as it enters the folding head. Any slight misalignment of the folded napkin from the folding head can greatly magnify error.

Measures such as adding a bond pattern to the tissue with an inline embosser to bond multiple plies and thus increase napkin strength can actually make the material more difficult to cut and register. Bonded materials can actually stick to the cutting blade in the cut point, creating a hole or rough edge while the blade punches through. These areas are the lowest quality areas of the napkin and must be removed. Due to difficulties with high-speed napkin punching, removal of these areas is a complicated process. An automated napkin inspection and rejection system using a sensor to detect napkin thickness variations to identify hole and low strength areas is a significant cost in both machinery and resultant scrap. In many cases, the material and machine complexity has resulted in an outright inability to cost-effectively automate production of particular napkin types.

The first challenge comes in the form of the raw material used to make the napkins. The raw material is a roll of low-basis weight paper which is hard to control due to its flimsy nature. This material is difficult to handle, more difficult to cut, and still more difficult to register cut length properly so as to control the final napkin size. This problem gets progressively more difficult with increases in production rate.

The production of quality household paper napkins requires both technological and manufacturing expertise. The high-speed, automated dispensing of a consistent, uniform napkin is an extremely complex process. There are several challenges in automating the napkin production process. (Frits & Bertok, 2020)(Wuest et al., 2020)(Sodhi et al.2023)

4. Implementation of automation technology

In order to create a system with the most effective production rate, a single lane serviette folder able to fold single ply material into the desired shape will be used in conjunction with a machine designed to feed and convey short term access storage or finishing machines. The folder receives its product from the previous process via a SCARA Type TRT robot. The robot has the ability to follow a predefined path and is designed to specialize in picking up blocks of paper. By using an image processing system, the robot can correctly locate and pick up the serviette and place it in the conveyor of the single lane folder. This process is quite time consuming at 40 seconds per serviette; however, it is the most effective folding method in terms of quality. Step-by-step instructions can be found in Appendix I.

Household serviettes are a disposable product that serves as a drying agent in the home. There are two main folds: the single fold and the double fold. Both folds contain two edges that need to be sealed in order to prevent the serviette from coming apart and fraying. The conventional method of producing household serviettes is using a folder to create a single fold. It is created by a slitter, which also makes an impression in the serviette to mark the halfway point so that the double fold can be done by a worker. The product is then sorted and hand packed. Recent breakthroughs in automation technology have provided us with the possibility of creating an automation system able to perform the specified tasks. (Deore et al., 2023)(Frits & Bertok, 2020)(Vieira et al., 2023)

5. Selection of automated machinery

Napkin production in the UK is littered with small and medium-sized enterprises that have failed to automate and still rely on antiquated machinery. The experiences of an engineer from a UK paper mill serve as a good example. Having visited a napkin manufacturer in Sweden, it was clear that substantial investment in automated machinery was necessary to achieve the goals stated above. However, the engineer's proposal to simply replace the worn-out napkin printing presses with modern, high-speed machines was not in line

with the Swedish manufacturer's forward-thinking plans.

Automated machinery has been used in industry for decades, although its application to the scale of the medium-sized enterprise is a different matter. The task faced by the medium-sized manufacturer is to firstly mechanize the production of napkins to a level which warrants the use of automatic inspection and packaging equipment, thus industrializing the process. A secondary reason, although no less important, is to allow for improvements in productivity of the production staff. This should be achieved by the transfer of 'skilled' manual jobs to those of machine minders and maintenance staff. Although these are new requirements for a UK napkin manufacturer, the experiences of others in the paper converting industry explain some of the successes and pitfalls that have been encountered. (Kalra and Tewari2024)(Deshpande et al.2023)(Calo, 2021)

6. Integration of automation into existing production line

The final stage was to conduct a factory acceptance test on the program and then install it on the machine. This was done by emulating the code from the design phase using RS Logix Emulate 500. This program simulates an Allen Bradley PLC and acts as an interface representing the input and output devices from the actual physical control. The code from the design phase was input into a ladder logic diagram to replicate the control sequence. This was a non-intrusive method of testing the control, as we were not modifying the program already on the machine. Any problems found during the F.A.T were then modified in the code design until it was problem-free. This was the desired control code and could be installed on the machine with confidence. RS Logix Emulate cost us time before the start of the project and during development, but it was definitely beneficial because it identified control sequence problems that could not have been found using the hard-wired testing method.

The replication of how the machine would operate identified vital information on how the machine could be improved and optimized with little to no cost. For example, ProModel was able to identify that the original control sequence for the pneumatic actuators was not optimized and

thus would cause the machine idle time. This was due to the valve control output. The original sequence was written to turn the valve on and off too quickly, which would sometimes cause the actuator to double actuate, resulting in no output at all. This meant changing the design of the code to increase the delay of the off output for the valve. This was done on the simulated version of the control, and when the machine was trialed with the new code, it was clear that there was an improvement.

Once the design was completed, the next step was to integrate the design and simulate the future output to identify any potential problems that may have been overlooked during the initial design. The simulation was done using ProModel, a program that uses event-driven scheduling to simulate a production line. A digital replica of the machine and the plant layout was created, and the code written during the design phase was input into the emulation of the machine to replicate the control output. By simulating the program, it was clear to see how the machine would operate within the plant. It predicted the cycle time of the product and also identified any potential flaws in the sequence of control. (Hur et al.2021)(Zhou et al.2024)(Maeschalck et al.2023)

7. Training and skill development for operators

Ensuring that the correct skills and knowledge are learned to perform these on-machine, near-machine, and off-machine tasks is key. Skill can be defined and measured in levels: a level of skill or knowledge can be seen as an individual having a clear understanding of what has to be done, how it has to be done, and to what standard it needs to be done. A skilled person can make complex inferences from situational information. High-skilled individuals are able to more readily adapt to the changes in their environment and perform a greater range of tasks. The aim is to raise the level of skill in each operator to perform their job with competency and to develop knowledge that will allow them to progress to higher levels within the firm.

In a previous research study, operator training was found to be important in the production of high-quality products. Operators employed in the project firms now have a higher

level of responsibility as they now have to operate and control machinery instead of working at manual tasks near the machines. They will also have to carry out basic machine maintenance and adjustments. With the introduction of electronically controlled machinery in the production of napkins, machine operatives must have a range of skills to work with precision, detect faulty conditions, and take remedial action. Interviews indicated that unskilled or poorly trained workers are more likely to make mistakes and induce product spoilage. This is clearly stated in the first part of the project when one operator tried using the CNC lathe to fabricate a part. He used the wrong type of cutter and cut the part undersized. With the increase in on-machine and near-machine tasks, there is a likelihood of productivity loss or wastage of material through faulty decision making by operators. (Watanabe et al.2022)(Tsaloumi & Koutsoumanis, 2024)(Magnaghi et al.2022)

8. Quality control measures in automated production

However, before implementing any control measures, a thorough analysis must be performed on the potential quality issues in the final product. The main focus of this analysis is to decide whether a particular issue can/cannot be fixed, is it cost effective to take measures to prevent it occurring, and how severe of an effect does it have on the product's fitness for use. The most effective way to perform this analysis is to get a group of people together to identify all potential problems and then vote on each problem's severity and what should be done to fix or prevent it. This will give each issue a quantifiable rank and will make it easier to determine which issues should be addressed.

The use of sophisticated technologies in manufacturing, coupled with complex operations, has resulted in an intensified need for quality control. While quality issues can be corrected as the product moves through the various stages of production, it's both cheaper and less time-consuming to prevent flaws or defects from occurring in the first place. A simple yet effective example of this is the "poke yoke" concept employed by the Japanese car. This technique employs simple fool-proof mechanisms to prevent a defect occurring. It may

be as simple as applying a certain sized and shaped pin between two components to ensure they are properly aligned before they are welded together. If the pin does not fit in the hole, the assembler knows immediately that there is a gap in the component alignment. By looking at the pin only, the assembler can determine that corrective action is required on the particular component. Equally simple and effective measures should be implemented in the automated production of Napkin Co.'s household napkins. (Arden et al.2021)(Li et al.2022)(Schmitt et al.2020)

9. Maintenance and troubleshooting of automated machinery

Though a planned maintenance system should prevent the breakdown of machinery, it is inevitable that the machinery will encounter problems or faults at some point. If the machinery has been developed using design, transient, or off-line fault finding techniques, there is often little information on the fault and the location in the machinery. This will make it difficult to diagnose a problem and determine whether the problem is an isolated case, which should be left and monitored, or whether immediate countermeasures should be taken. In the case that immediate countermeasures are necessary, the cost to stop the machinery and carry out repairs must be weighed against the risk of secondary damage due to continued operation. A cost-benefit analysis considering the present and future predicted states of the machinery can be used to determine whether to carry out repairs or to continue operation and stop the machine at a scheduled time.

The maintenance of machinery in the production of household paper products is a key factor in assuring maximum efficiency. To avoid delays and interruptions in production, a planned maintenance system is necessary. There are a number of checklist items to go through when inspecting the system, such as component and parts replacement, lubrication, fault finding to prevent breakdowns, electrical maintenance, and maintenance management. The maintenance schedule should be based on the mode and function of components, and factors such as long-term trend in breakdown frequency and sudden failures should be taken into account to

continuously review and upgrade the system. Planned maintenance can prevent the seven forms of loss in production and manufacturing (defects, waiting, transportation, inventory, motion, and overproduction) and will allow the machinery to be in its optimum running condition. (Aheleroff et al.2020)(Ayvaz & Alpaya, 2021)(Nandi et al.2021)

10. Cost analysis of implementing automation

Assessing the costs and value of automation constitutes a very broad and complex analysis. There is a variety of ways to consider the benefits that could potentially be realized from introducing automation; every approach has its own strengths and weaknesses. Essentially, the value of using automation is the difference in outcomes from using it to the outcome of not using it. One approach may be to consider the potential loss of revenue from not investing in the technology. It could be that competitors could use the technology to create a more cost-effective product or to reduce the price of their current product to a point where it is no longer feasible to produce the product manually at a competitive price. This approach is often quite subjective and difficult to quantify, although it could lead to an assumption that there is a value up to the potential loss. On a different approach, more precise estimates could be produced. Another way to consider the value of automation would be to weigh the long-term costs of developing and running an automated system against the possible cost savings and benefits it could bring compared to the task being done manually. This is the approach we have taken to consider the costs and benefits of automating the process of producing napkins. (Collins et al.2021)

11. Return on investment (ROI) calculation

Step 3 aims to maximize the sum of annual net return over the entire period, whereby the bond repayment model states that the difference between the rate of interest and the rate of a loan to repay a sum of money M is equivalent to annual repayment $(S-M)$. This will involve a situation where the annual net return is equal to the interest rate. Changes to the time of the investment will cause an opportunity to increase the interest rate, and therefore the aim is to delay the investment to gain the highest interest rate on

the net return. The final year at which there is net return is the year in which the investment occurs.

The date of implementation of the investment must be considered to determine a suitable interest rate. Step 2 involves correcting the annual rate of interest, where it can be determined from an interest rate on an alternative investment of equal risk or if the investment will prevent an alternative loan or a reinvestment of capital.

A useful method for the calculation of ROI of the napkin manufacturing line is through cashflow analysis, which will start with an estimation of expenditure and revenue for future years. This can be detailed as seen in table 1. Using the ROI, step 1 involves setting time periods where the net return of the investment between changes in capital and the capital cost. Changes between positive and negative net return can be considered as separate investments, and capital cost must be allocated in the period in which it is used. Step 1 ends when the net return reaches a value C.

The net return is the annualized return from the investment excluding the capital itself. This will include costs saved and any additional revenue brought in by the investment. The timeframe for the net return and capital must be the same, as must be the currency. The capital cost of the investment is the total sum of money used to achieve the return. Decreasing the capital cost for an equal net return will increase the ROI.

$$ROI = (R-C)/C \quad (1)$$

Return on investment (ROI) is a financial concept that helps us understand what the return will be on a particular investment given today's money. We are, in fact, comparing the return in future currency to today's currency as we can only spend what we have now. If the return on the investment is 0, this means that the return is only enough to compensate for the time value of money. The calculation of ROI is displayed in equation (1) where R is the net return of the investment and C is the capital cost of the investment. (Dadd and Hinton2023)

12. Environmental impact of automated production

There has been rapid growth in the production of disposable paper products over the past several decades. Napkins, paper towels, and

facial tissues have become an indispensable part of households in many developed countries. Over half of all napkins used in the United States are purchased for use away from the home. Increased consumption of these products has led to concern about solid waste disposal, deforestation, and effects on global climate. Market growth and increased consumption of napkins have led to automation which can be modeled as a microeconomic cost-minimizing choice best responding to a change in relative factor prices. Costs of automated production are represented by an output elasticity of capital (-.53), an output elasticity of energy (-.25), an output elasticity of materials (-.18), an input share equation, and constraint on the capital and energy prices.

The environmental impact of automating a particular product depends on the relationship of its inputs and outputs with the environment. Its greater efficiency in converting inputs to outputs could greatly reduce environmental impact or it could increase total throughput of materials and energy. The diverse possibilities for automation make it difficult to generalize about environmental effects. Automation usually increases productivity and makes more efficient use of materials, so effects of this type of change come from expansion or contraction of the industry. If the industry expands by producing more of the same product, the assumption of an elastic demand implies that more output will increase total throughput of materials and energy. If the increased productivity causes a shift to more automated or capital-intensive methods, higher skilled workers who lose their jobs might find work in other industries. This could lead to retraining or displacement costs in the short run, but in the long run it would require more education to acquire the skills needed for other jobs. It is difficult to say what the net effect on the environment would be because of the many other factors that influence environmental policy and technological change. (Hameed et al.2024)

13. Market analysis for automated household napkins

The current global market for household napkin production is showing a steady growth as the technology and demand are growing in the 21st century. An average household uses and disposes of napkins between 2-4 times a day.

Currently, the North American and European regions make up 60% of the total global market. However, due to the increased demand for napkins in the Asia Pacific and Latin American regions, there is an expected increase in growth in these areas of nearly 40% over the next 5-6 years. Of the global market, 68% of napkins purchased are the standard 1-ply cellulose napkin. However, it is expected that there will be a decline in the 1-ply napkin use and an increase in the 2-ply napkin use. The market for the production of napkins is done regionally, thus napkins are manufactured and sold within the region. This gives a huge opportunity for napkin producers as they can distribute their product within the region at a relatively low cost. It is expected that there will be large increases in production in the Asia Pacific and Latin American regions in efforts to supply the increased demand for napkins.

14. Future trends in automation for household napkin production

It is also likely that the napkin industry will adopt packaging automation trends being developed currently in the tissue industry as this will represent a cost-effective solution to an increase in napkin manufacturing automation. Alternative napkin packaging methods could also become the target of automation for the future. High-pressure packer/stackers and paper napkin banding machinery to replace current clear film overwrap banding technologies are examples of automation which can pave the way for faster and more cost-effective packaging methods.

Manual assembly of household paper napkins does not appear to have any immediate replacement as current production rates can easily be matched with automatic high-speed packaging equipment. Today, however, the trend is more towards one-stop conversion and packaging lines. With the advent of high-yield

nonwovens technologies, the lines between paper and nonwovens products will become increasingly blurred. High-speed paper napkin folder, embossers, and printing presses will be required for nonwovens napkin production. However, nonwovens embossing and printing technologies will have to catch up as the majority of this equipment is currently built to serve the tissue industry. Specialized machinery capable of multi-ply nonwovens lamination with high production rates may also be required for future nonwovens napkin production. This is a far cry from the manual napkin assembly methods used with nonwovens and will certainly increase demand for automation in this sector.

15. Conclusion The main aim of the project is to establish the complete automation for the production of household napkins. The report explores the various technologies and techniques that are used in the development of automation for the production process. The interesting result is that there are substantial improvements compared to the conventional napkin production process. The automation is targeted for small or medium industry. The major advantages are the reduced production cost as the salary for a worker is increasing and the few workers can handle all the processes in the production. Other advantages include the improvement of product quality and the reduction of time for product development. The simulation tests and the actual trials prove that the system is suitable and reliable for the target industry. With a little effort and investment, it is worth to apply this automation for the napkin production process. A future enhancement can be added to the system to automatically develop a new type of product or to handle the logistics of the product to the retailer. (Arafat & Uddin, 2022)(Salunke et al.2024)(Mehtar, 2022)

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